

A Retrospective Observational Study of Dead on Arrival (DOA) Cases in the first Ever Triage-based Emergency Department in Bangladesh

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Abstract

Background: The Emergency Department (ED) is the main entry point where patients first meet healthcare personnel in case of a health emergency in Bangladesh, where there is currently no existing organized pre-hospital care system or emergency medicine specialty available. The aim of this study was to describe patterns, associated comorbidities, time of incident, health-seeking behavior, treatment provided and average time to reach the hospital for people that were dead on arrival (DOA). **Methods:** Data of DOA cases for this study were collected from ED, 250 Bed District Sadar Hospital, Cox's Bazaar, a tertiary level hospital in Bangladesh with an average patient turnover of 350 per day. A specific structured data collection format (figure 1) was developed for the patients who were declared as DOA by an ED physician, and then data were collected from 1st January '23 to 30th June '23. **Results:** A total of 437 patients were declared as DOA in the ED within the six-month study period. Among them, 62% were male, and 38% were female. The age group with the largest proportion of DOA were the newborn (22.2%, n=97), followed by those aged between 46 and 50 years (20.6%, n=90). Most patients came from Cox's Bazar Sadar Upazila (37.1%, n=262). A large number (57.7%, n=252) came from home and received no formal healthcare support before arriving at the ED. Regarding contributing past history, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) was the primary factor and mainly involved those >60 years. Among the newborn deaths, the cause of death was determined to be cord not being clamped in 19.6% (n=19) of cases. Of the 97 cases of newborn DOA, 44.3% (n=43) had a history of delivery at home. Among all DOA cases, a further 62 (14.2%) had a cause of death determined as unnatural, predominantly either from assault or road trauma, and predominantly in the working age group. Considering Forcibly Displaced Myanmar Nationals in Bangladesh (FDMN) people, in spite of being nearly double in population comparing with the host community of a selected area, this study found DOA cases were less than half (28.7%) among them. **Conclusion:** This study was the first in Bangladesh to describe the pattern of deaths amongst DOA cases in an ED. Most DOA cases presented directly from home with no formal prehospital care. There was a particularly high proportion of newborns among the DOA cases. Available standard prehospital care with ambulance service and education on health seeking behavior specially during pregnancy or childbirth needs urgent attention. Government collaboration with other organizations will ensure the quality health services and reduce the unexpected prehospital deaths.

Keywords: Dead on arrival, Emergency Department, Unnatural death, Pre-hospital care.

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Introduction:

Dead on arrival (DOA) is defined as the people who are dead when brought to a hospital. (1)Dead on arrival (DOA) broadly refers to patients who were either declared dead upon arrival to an emergency department (ED) with no resuscitation attempt or those who died after failed resuscitation, usually within the first 15 to 60 minutes of arrival.(2). Pre-hospital care is known to reduce DOA cases at hospital. (2),(3),(4)

The ED is the gateway to the hospital in Bangladesh. There is no formal pre-hospital care in Bangladesh, the exception being in the setting of corporations at considerable cost. No established standard public ambulance service is available, so patients usually attend to ED by their own cost of transport like paddle rickshaw, three wheeler autorickshaw, or sometimes ambulance if referred from another health facility.

Emergency medicine is not established in Bangladesh yet. As a result, most ED work is as a “traffic station”.

The ED physician’s role is only as a “ticket clerk“ to send the patients to their respective ward, assessing them only by taking a short history sometimes with a prior signed form without attending the patients. As an example, chest pain patients go to the general medicine ward, abdominal pain patients traditionally go to the surgery ward, pregnant patients and patients in labour go to the obstetrics and gynecology ward, most without initial assessment in the ED. In a setup like this, DOA cases are registered in a register book where only a patient’s personal information like address and the contact number of relatives is noted manually for medicolegal purposes. For this reason, there is no available previous study on emergency medicine or DOA in Bangladesh.

This study was conducted in the first and only-triage based public hospital ED at 250 Bed District Sadar Hospital, Cox’s Bazar which is also supporting the

emergency care response for the world’s largest refugee (Forcefully Displaced Myanmar Nationalities, FDMN) crisis. In 2020, the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) established the first and only triage-based ED in Cox’s Bazar with the co-operation of the Bangladesh government and provided support with infrastructure, logistics, training along with the support of other NGOs including International Organisation for Migration (IOM) and Community Partners International(CPI)(5). From the beginning of this initiative, the team tried to develop and practice standard emergency services through collaboration with world-renowned emergency medicine specialists from around the globe. To ensure effective emergency care, ICRC facilitated multiple phases of capacity building activities.. This study is the result of that effort and analyses the first documentation of DOA cases. The aim of this study was to describe DOA cases and then determine the causes, precipitating factors, demographic patterns, co-morbidities of these DOA cases.

Methods & Materials:

This was a retrospective study carried out in the first and only triage-based ED of Bangladesh in 250 Bed District Sadar Hospital, Cox’s Bazar. At first a registration tool (Figure 1) was designed to collect data in a structured way. Then data were collected from 1st January 2023 to 30th June 2023. The history of illness, informing the potential causes of death, was extracted from relatives or by the persons who brought the patients to ED. Analyses

were conducted using Microsoft Excel. **Results:** The total number of patients who attended the ED as DOA was 437 during the 6 month period from 1st January

2023 to 30th June 2023. **Gender & age:** Out of 437 cases, 269 (61.6%) were males and 168 (38.4%) were females. Regarding age distribution, most DOA cases (n=97, 22.2%) were newborn, i.e. day of delivery. Those aged between 46-60 years represented 20.6% (n=90) of DOA cases. (Table 1)

Age	Male	Female	Total	%
0 day	57	40	97	22.2%
1-28 days	8	5	13	3.0%
29-59 days	5	3	8	1.8%
2 months- 1 year	15	8	23	5.3%
>1 year-5 years	10	9	19	4.4%
>5 years-14 years	7	3	10	2.3%
15 years-29 years	18	19	37	8.5%
30 years-45 years	37	20	57	13.0%
46 years-60 years	57	33	90	20.6%
> 60 years	55	28	83	19.0%
Total	269	168	437	100%

Table 1: Number of cases of different age groups

History of cause of death:

According to the history of cause of death which was extracted from patients' relatives or caregiver most patients (29.1%, n=127) had a history of loss of consciousness (LOC), shortness of breath (SOB) (11.2%,n=49). Other preceding symptoms documented were chest pain (5.7%,n=25), chest pain and SOB combined (3.5%, n=15), fever and febrile convulsion (2.8%,n=12) and diarrhea(2.5%,n=11). Total 51 cases (11.6%) came with a history of injury (Table 2).

Histoty of cause of death	Number	%
Loss of conciosness	127	29.06%
Shortness of breath	49	11.21%
Chest pain	25	5.72%
Chest pain & SOB	15	3.43%
Neonatal complications	110	25.17%
Trauma & other injuries	51	11.67%
Poisoing	3	0.69%
Gyne & Obs cause	11	2.52%
Fever & febrile convulsion	12	2.75%
Diarrhoea	11	2.52%
Pneumonia	12	2.75%
Septicemia	2	0.46%
Others	8	1.83%
Invalid data	1	0.23%
Total	437	100%

Table 2: History of cause of death. *EONS=Early onset neonatal sepsis, **PNA=perinatal asphyxia, ***SOB= Shortness of breath.

Among trauma & other injuries road traffic accidents (RTA) were the highest in number (25.5%, n=13) followed by physical assault (21.57%,n=11), hangning (19.6%, n=10),electrocution (11.76%, n=6),drowning (5.9%, n=3) and other accidental injuries (e.g. landslide, accidental fall from height etc) were (9.8%,n=5). Two cases had a history of choking and one had history of fire incident. (Table 3)

In the neonate age group (25.2%,n=110), most patients presented with a history of perinatal asphyxia (70.9%, n=78), cord not clamped in newborn (17.3%,n=19), early onset neonatal sepsis (10.0%,n=11), or neonatal jaundice (1.9%,n=2).

Trauma & other injuries	Number	Column1
Accidental injury	5	9.80%
Drowning	3	5.88%
Electrocution	6	11.76%
Fire incident	1	1.96%
Hanging	10	19.61%
Physical assault	11	21.57%
RTA	13	25.49%
Choking	2	3.92%
Total	51	100%

Table 3: Trauma & related history of cause of death
In the neonate age group (25.2%,n=110), most patients presented with a history of perinatal asphyxia (70.9%, n=78), cord not clamped in newborn (17.3%,n=19), early onset neonatal sepsis (10.0%,n=11), or neonatal jaundice (1.9%,n=2).

History of Cause of Death in neonates	Number	%
PNA	78	70.9%
Cord not clamped	19	17.2%
EONS	11	10.0%
NNJ	2	1.8%
Total	110	100%

Table 4: History of cause of death in neonates

Among the 168 female patients, 6.6% (11) had a history of gynecological or obstetric complications in which three were post-partum hemorrhage (PPH), three were ruptured ectopic pregnancies, with one case of ruptured uterus and one with eclampsia (Table 4).

Gyne & Obs causes	Number
Unknown Obstetric Complication	3
PPH	3
Ruptured ectopic pg	3
Ruptured uterus	1
Eclampsia	1
Total	11

Table 5: Death due to gyne. & obs. related causes.

Few patients(n=8) came with “other” (i.e. not specified) history among which three patients had no known history as bystanders took them to ED and, as they were considered an unnatural death, were sent to morgue for post mortem as medicolegal cases(Table 5).

Others	Number
Acute hepatic failure	1
GIT perforation	2
Hematemesis	1
Dengue shock syndrome	1
Unknown	3
Total	8

Table 6: Others history of cause of death

Place	Number	%
Home	252	57.7%
Govt Hospital	113	25.9%
Clinic	30	6.9%
Camp health facility	8	1.8%
Others	34	7.8%
Total	437	100%

Table 7: Location (resident vs health facilities)

Figure 2: FDMN Vs as Bangladeshi DOA.

Location: Total 286 (65.5%) patients came from home & other places (excluding roads, beach) without receiving any primary treatment while only 151 (34.6%) came from different health facilities. (Table 6)

Regarding the origins of patients from the various upazilas of Cox's Bazar, most cases came from Cox's Bazar Sadar Upazila (37.1%, n=162) followed by Ramu (13.5%, n=59), Chakaria (6.0%, n=26), Eidgaon (4.9%, n=21),

Upazila	Number	%
Chakaria	26	5.9%
Cox's Bazar Sadar	162	37.0%
Eidgaon	21	4.8%
Kutubdia	3	1.0%
Maheshkhali	32	7.3%
Pekua	4	1.0%
Ramu	59	13.5%
Teknaf	33	7.6%
Ukhia	54	12.3%
Others	37	8.5%
Unknown	4	1.0%
Invalid data	2	0.4%
Total	437	100%

Table 8: Location (Differents Upazila)

Kutubdia (1.0%, n=3), Maheshkhali (7.32%, n=32), Pekua (0.9%, n=4), Teknaf (7.6%, n=33) Ukhia (12.4%, n=54) & Others (8.5%, n=37). There were four patients who were brought to ED without proper identity & address, counted as unnatural death. Two cases had incomplete data (Table 7)

Forcibly Displaced Myanmar Nationals in Bangladesh (FDMN): In 2017 more than one million Rohingya fled from Myanmar and came to Bangladesh as refugees (7) They live in Ukhia and Teknaf upazila in the largest refugee camp in the world supported by different international NGOs and the Bangladesh government.

They are receiving healthcare support from different camp health facilities as well as from Ukhiya, Teknaf upazila health complex and from 250 Bed District Sadar Hospital.(8) Total 25 (5.7%) patients were FDMN people in this study (Figure 2).

It is observed that from Ukhiya & Teknaf upazila total 87 patients came to ED as DOA. Among which 62(71.3%) were Bangladeshi citizen who came to this higher center without proper referral or ambulance services as like from other areas .In the other hand only 25 (28.7%) FDMN people were received as DOA (Table 8). All of them were escorted by proper ambulance services provided by different NGOs which significantly indicates that effective referral and minimum support during transport can reduce the burden indeed.

Arrival time: Most of the cases (17.2%, n=75) arrived at the hospital between 12 pm to 3 pm followed by the time period from 9 am to 12 pm (14.7%, n=64) (Table 9).

Time	Number	%
6am-9am	41	9.4%
9am-12pm	64	14.7%
12pm-3pm	75	17.2%
3pm-6pm	59	13.5%
6pm-9pm	54	12.4%
9pm-12am	61	14.0%
12am-3am	43	9.8%
3am-6am	40	9.2%
Total	437	100%

Table 9 : Arrival time

Past histories:

Among neonates, 90 cases presented with a history of complicated labor. Others, with a history of low birth weight, very low birth weight and preterm cases were 16 in number. Excluding neonates, the most common past history was COPD (57 cases).

The next most common past history was unremarkable or undetermined in the case of unnatural death s (50 cases) which underwent post-mortem for medico-legal purposes. Other conditions were diabetes mellitus (45 cases), hypertension (39 cases). A total of 41(9.4%) cases had no significant past history. There were seven cases of malnourished children with complications who attended the ED, all of whom were under five years old. Pneumonia and respiratory tract infection (RTI) represented the highest proportion of cases (n=17, xx.x%) among children aged between one and five years.. Considering the given history and conditions by caregiver or relatives of dead on arrival cases, six were diagnosed with neoplasm which included Ca esophagus (two), oral cancer (one) , adenocarcinoma (one), leukemia (one) and cholangiocarcinoma (one)(Table 10).

Population	Number	%
Bangladeshi	62	71.3%
FDMN	25	28.7%
Total	87	100%

Table 10 : Arrival time FDMN Vs Bangladeshi

Past histories	0 day	1-28 days	29-59 days	2 months-1 year	>1-5 years	>5-14 years	15-29 years	30-45 years	46-60 years	> 60 years	Total
ACS							1				1
AF									1		1
AMI								1	1		2
Anemia						1		1			2
Aspiration					1						1
Asthma				1				1	1		3
BEP								1			1
CHD				1		1					2
Chicken pox				1	1						2
CKD						1		1	3	1	6
CLD										1	1
Complicated labor*	86	4									90
Congenital anomalies	1										1
COPD								3	26	28	57
CRHD									1		1
Dead in bead										1	1
DM								9	15	21	45
Fever			1	3	3		1				8
Foreign body ingestion				1							1
Gynae & obs. complications							7				7
Hepatitis							1				1
HTN							1	7	16	15	39
ICM									2	2	4
IHD								8	12	22	42

Jaundice **						1						1
LBW ,VLBW & Pre term	11	5	1									17
Malnutrition				6	1							7
Multiple pregnancy	5											5
Neoplasm						1	1		1		4	7
Niana ingestion***				2								2
NNJ		2										2
Not specified	1	2	1	2	3		4	11	10		7	41
NSTEMI											1	1
Pneumonia & RTI			5	9	3			1				18
Post dated pregnancy	1											1
SAIO									1			1
Septicemia							1					1
STEMI									1			1
Stroke & CVD								2	12		15	29
TB								1			2	3
Unnatural death				1	3	7	17	20	11		3	62
Vomiting							1					1
Invalid data							1					1

*Complicated labor= history of delivery of baby after long time of failed home trial, **Jaundice= not classified,*** Niana ingestion= local traditional medicine for children which composite is still unknown.

Table 11: Defferents Cases Arriaved in Emergency

ACS=acute coronary syndrome, AF= atrial fibrillation, AMI= acute myocardial ischemia, BEP=benign enlargement of prostate, CHD= congenital heart disease, CLD= chronic liver disease, CKD= chronic kidney disease, COPD= chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, CRHD= chronic rheumatic heart disease, DM= diabetes mellitus, HTN= hypertension, ICM= ischemic cardiomyopathy, IHD= ischemic heart disease, LBW= low birth weight, VLBW= very low birth weight, NNJ= neonatal jaundice, NSTEMI= non ST elevated myocardial infraction, RTI= respiratory tract infection, SAIO= sub-acute intestinal obstruction, STEMI= ST elevated myocardial infraction, CVD= cardiovascular disease, TB= tuberculosis

Come from	Number	%
Home	43	44.3%
Facilities	54	55.7%
Total	97	100%

Table 12: Newborn from home vs health facilities

Figure 3: Area distribution of newborn DOA cases.

DOA in newborn: Among DOA cases, 22.2% were newborn (n=97). Among them 57 (58.8%) were male and 40 (41.2%) were female (Table 1). The majority of newborn cases (55.7%, n=54) came from different health facilities and 44.3% of them (n=43) came from home with a history of home delivery- (Table 12). At home, usually delivery was done by unskilled half trained traditional birth attendants who trialed the patients for a long time. Among the newborn DOA cases most (25.8%, n=25) were from the area nearest to 250 Bed District Sadar hospital. Most of these (21 cases) were delivered at home. Second most number from Moheshkhali (14.4%, n=14). Among other areas of origin, there were 15 cases from Ramu, 11 from Chakaria, an 6 from Ukhia..(Figure 3)

Cord not clamped in newborn: Among newborn patients, 19 cases (19.6%) came with an attached placenta (Table 13). Most of these cases came from Cox's Bazar Sadar area (11 cases). Two cases came from health facilities in Teknaf (Table 14)

Neonates	Number	%
Cord not clamped	19	19.6%
Others	78	80.4%
Total	97	100%

Table 13: Cord not clamped in newborn percentage

Upazila	Home	Hospital
Chakaria	0	0
Cox's bazar Sadar	11	
Eidgaon	0	0
Kutubdia	0	0
Moheshkhali	0	0
Pekua	0	0
Ramu	3	0
Teknaf	3	2
Ukhia	0	0
Total	17	2

Table 14: Cord not clamped in newborn distribution area.

DOA	Others	%
Unnatural death	62	14.2%
Others	375	85.8%
Total	437	100

Table 15: Unnatural death percentage as DOA

Unnatural death: An unnatural death results from an external cause, typically including homicides, suicides, accidents, medical errors, alcohol intoxications and drug overdoses. Jurisdictions differ in how they categorize and report unnatural deaths, including level of detail and whether they are considered a single category with subcategories, or separate top-level categories. There is no international standard on whether or how to classify a death as natural vs. unnatural.

(9) In this study, a total of 62 (14.19%) cases came with a history of unnatural death (Table 15). The most common causes of unnatural death were RTA (20.9%,n=13), followed by

Figure 4: Unnatural death

physical assault (17.7%, n=11) and hanging (16.1%, n=10)(- Figure 4).

High yield group: The number of cases with ages ranging from 15-45 years were 42.1% (184), among which 58.5% (55) were male & 41.5% (39) were female (Table 16)

Co-morbidities in high yield group people: In working group (15-45 years) people the majority (39.37%,n=37) had a history of unnatural death. Among other histories, 15.9% (n=15) patients had no specific history while IHD and HTN (8.5%,n=8) number was the same in this age group and 9.58% (n=9) patients had history of DM (Table 17).

Age group	Number	%
High yield age	184	42.1%
Others	253	57.9%
Total	437	100%

Table 16: Percentage of high yield age as DOA.

Past histories	15 years-29 years	30 years-45 years	Total
ACS	1		1
AMI		1	1
Anemia		1	1
Asthma		1	1
BEP		1	1
CKD		1	1
COPD		3	3
DM		9	9
Fever	1		1
Gynae & obs complications	7		7
Hepatitis	1		1
HTN	1	7	8
IHD		8	8
Neoplasm	1		1
Not specified	4	11	15
Pneumonia & RTI		1	1
Septicemia	1		1
Stroke & CVD		2	2
TB		1	1
Unnatural death	17	20	37
Vomiting	1		1
Invalid data	1		1

Table 17: Past histories of high yield group

DISCUSSION: This study described the burden and characteristics of DOA cases in a tertiary level hospital in Bangladesh. There are few published studies regarding DOA and almost all of the them are from countries where EDs are well established and documentation is well preserved. To our knowledge, until now, there are no such studies from Bangladesh.

This study is one of the first attempts to perform a limited situation analysis of the DOA cases presented to one of the densely populated costal area of Bangladesh.

Our study showed the total number of DOA cases with multitude of different presentations with highest (25.2%) rate in neonatal age (10) like a study showed in India. (11) Among which 3.0% cases were age range from 1 day to 28 days presented with the complications like EONS, LBW & VLBW. In our study gave emphasis on the cases which are of 0 day age. Because it's the highest (22.2%) range age group.

In the range of age group who were attended to ED second maximum number seen in 46-60 years (20.59%), in >60 years (18.99%) and in 30-45 years (13.04%) respectively. This result is different from a study in Nepal (12), where highest age group was 31-45 years, a study in Ghana (13), where highest age group was >70 years, a study in Pakistan (2), where highest age group was 20-29 years. Age distribution in our study excluding neonates reflects that most of the DOA cases were in the prime of their lives mainly.

Regarding past history in adults, COPD was the highest in number which is similar to Nepal. (12) Among others diabetes and hypertension both were present in mostly above thirty age group patients with an increasing trend seen among 45-60 years and beyond cases. Ischemic heart disease (IHD) was also very much alarming below 45 years those who were dead on arrival. Stroke and cardiovascular disease (CVD) was as usual in 45 to above 60 years of age (27 cases).

In this study, 9.4% cases didn't have any known specific past history. Most of them belong to age group 30-45 years which is also similar with study in Nepal (12) & Ghana. (13)

Most of the cases (17.2%), came to ED between 12pm to 3 pm. This corresponds to the time they need to get to this tertiary center after being referred from periphery UHC during morning doctor visiting hour which usually at 9 am. Second most time number (14.7%) was 9 am to 12 pm. This time indicates that at first hour of the day patient party might have found the transport & start the journey for hospital & reach after 2-3 hours. This is different from Bharati et al. (12)

Distant to hospital has a major effect in mortality, more distance to hospital reduce the chance of survival (14) However, in our study, majority of cases (37.1%) came from Cox's Bazar Sadar area which ranged about 5 kilometers. This indicates distance alone might be not the only affecting factors but a combination of psychological, social and economic factors (13) (15).

Significant numbers of unnatural death ranging from under five to extreme age group were very alarming (14.2%). Most common cause of unnatural death was RTA (22.6%), like Khurshed et al. (2). Among unnatural death 17.8% came with history of physical assault, all of them were male. Six patients

had history of electrocution, all of them were below 30 years & all of them were also male. While exploring for the cause of this much male cases, we found in a study that accident and suicide mortality rates of men are 2-13 and 2-3 times those of women, respectively & women have 47% and 73% lower risks of any death and unnatural death than men, respectively (16). In all age group male cases (61.6%) are predominant than female (38.4%) which supports other studies as well. (2), (12), (13) Suicide is the second leading cause of death between the ages of 15-29 in the world. (17) In our study 6 patients presented with history of unnatural death in this age group & all of them (three poisoning & three hanging) had history of suicide which were supported by post-mortem report.

Working age group is defined as 15-64 years. (18) But Bangladesh is an agricultural country & in developing world working age in agriculture is less than 45 years according to an African study (19). For this, we consider 15 years -45 years as high yield age group. In this age group most common (39.4%, n=36) history was unnatural death (ex. RTA, accidental injury, poisoning, hanging) which is similar to a death report of Australia (20) Among others, DM (9.6%, n=9), HTN & IHD (8.5%, n=8) were the next most past histories in these age group.

Can pre-hospital care, standard referral & ambulance system reduce the death on the road?

Majority of patients (65.5%) came from home & other places without getting any primary aid. Relatives of these cases gave the history of onset of the symptoms (ex. LOC, chest pain, SOB) or after any incident (ex. accidental injury, RTA) at the home or any places, as there was no pre-hospital care system, they just by any local transport with their own cost reached to ED with a hope that they will get the maximum support at the terminal stage. During transport there were no existing standard care or neither trained personnel to aid the patients. It is seen that even from a health facility after being casual attended by physician or paramedic, cases are referred to higher center without prior communication or proper documentation regarding receiving status or clinical conditions of the diseased. Possible extracted history gathered from caregiver demonstrates that most of cases collapse suddenly at home or on the way to hospital. For that reason, highest number of LOC cases (29.3%) were received as DOA. Around 25% of people with T2D taking insulin for >5 years are found to have severe hypoglycemic events in the world. (21) If patients with history of DM can simply had a pre-hospital care with a CBG check

facility, they might be saved. In co-morbidities, patients with history of IHD, AMI, NSTEMI, AF and in history patients with symptoms of chest pain (5.8%) & history of chest pain & SOB (3.4%) had a better chance of survival with pre-hospital care. In this case we can remember that, sudden cardiac death is usually caused by a catastrophic arrhythmia and accounts for 25%–30% of all deaths from cardiovascular disease, claiming an estimated 70 000 to 90 000 lives each year in the UK. Many of these deaths are potentially preventable. (22)

Among age of 0 day cases (55.7%) were from different health facilities. It's a good sign that more people are seeking hospital based EOC treatment but due to lack of proper ambulance service it's going in vain. We also revealed a bitter truth that out of newborn (0 day) DOA cases large number (19.6%) of baby brought to ED with umbilical cord along with placenta in uncut position with a misbelief that still their lives remaining in the placenta or in the "life cord". Almost all them (n=17) come from home with history of delivery at home by untrained traditional Dai. Highest number (n=11) came from Cox's Bazar Sadar area. This study shows that number of DOA cases age of 0 day is higher than the number of still birth cases in the whole Cox's Bazar district. (23) Considering gender, most of newborn were male (58.8%). probably all of them could be saved if proper pre-hospital care were available.

In case of unnatural death RTA (22.6%), physical assault (17.7%), these trauma patients might be saved by first level responders & trained paramedics. (4)

Most important finding of our study about reduction of DOA cases by introducing pre-hospital care & ambulance service is, considering two Upazilas of Cox's Bazar, population of Teknaf is 2,63,389 (24) & Ukhiya is 2,07,379 (25) which makes total 4,70,768. In this two Upazilas total FDMN people are 9,32,204 (26) which is almost double than host people. But when we compared DOA cases among these area surprisingly in case of FDMN, DOA cases were less than half (28.7%, n=25). Many NGOs are supporting health sectors of FDMN along with Bangladesh Govt. & built a proper referral system with standard ambulance which ensures proper documentation, trained manpower in ambulance & a guidelines. It's not like that Bangladeshi people have no access in those facilities but these facilities are in refugee camp area which is a long distance journey from host community. These findings indicate if government takes partners in healthcare system, service would be improved & mortality would be reduced dramatically.

LIMITATIONS: This study have many limitations. Firstly, due to lack of documentation and a referral system we depend on verbal statements of patients' attendance for history in most cases such as loss of consciousness, shortness of breath, chest pain etc. Doctors are not acquainted with pre-hospital care and do not maintain proper referral notes. In most cases they write just "ref to ABC hospital" and nothing more before sending patients to tertiary hospitals. Secondly, there is no similar type of study in Bangladesh before, so it is difficult to compare. Often patients came by local transport like paddle rickshaw, three wheeler autorickshaws of their own and forget to bring previous treatment documents, as a result total picture of co-morbidities could not be achieved. Moreover due to lack of communication between health facilities & in absence of accessible health data archive, it is impossible to find out about previous treatment & morbidities. In most cases, one patient had multiple co-morbidities, for which percentage of co-morbidities was not calculated. Thirdly, there is no definitive understanding about the proportion of population engaged in the workforce according to age. So, we considered working age group based on norms in the agricultural workforce. Fourthly, in this study some data were entered as Invalid due to being missing. Nonetheless, this study will help further research about DOA and pre-hospital care in Bangladesh in a more structural way.

Opportunities for further research: By introducing the DOA data collection tool used in this article in the periphery level health facilities, involving ambulance services about the death of the referred patients on the way and establishing communications between health facilities, more specific information would be identified regarding reducing DOA number.

CONCLUSION: This study reveals that a large number of people are dying on the road without getting minimum healthcare service on the way. But pre-hospital care, trained manpower and documentation can reduce this number. It also indicates that motivating health seeking behavior of people by public education may have a huge impact on DOA rate, especially on reducing neonatal cases. Most importantly, this study shows that combination of government and other organizations (in this case NGOs) works better for reducing the number of preventable deaths.

COURTESY: All emergency medical officers (EMO) of 250 Bed District Sadar Hospital, Cox's Bazar who have worked during the study period (Dr. Shahir Fowaz Khan, Dr. Tayab, Dr. Ashim Sutradhar, Dr. Rafsan Islam, Dr. Tonmoy Habib, Dr. Mustasin Huda Khan, Dr. A. Kahar, Dr. Renessa Islam, Dr. Raihan, Dr. Shopnil Barua, Dr. Amit Das, Dr. Adnan, Dr. Misbah Uddin, Dr. S.M. Ashrafuzzaman)

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